

CLEAN AVIATION

**DESIGN OF A WIND TUNNEL MODEL
FOR FLUTTER INVESTIGATION OF
STRUT-BRACED HIGH ASPECT
RATIO WING IN THE FRAMEWORK
OF CS2-THT U-HARWARD PROJECT**

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Validation of the strut braced wing concept from an aeroelastic point of view, since conceptual design phase

1. Development and validation of tools for the geometrical non-linear structural behavior
2. Experimental validation of the SBW concept in wind tunnel

WHY the TBW? It is one of the most promising configurations for the new green A/C

Credit: NASA

THE AIRCRAFT

- Same class of an A320
- High mounted SBW
- Fuselage mounted engines
- AR=19
- Sized using NeoCASS

- The unconventional configuration requires physical based tools to estimate structural and non-structural masses, statistical approaches (Raymer, Torenbeek) are not valid because there isn't a statistical sample!

- Sizing performed using NeoCASS: CS25 compliant maneuvers to get the sizing loads and perform a fully stressed design of the structural components

- Analysis: is linear trim still valid? => Non-linear trim tool
- Does trim equilibrium affect aeroelastic stability? => Flutter on deformed A/C
- Strut impact on aeroelastic stability => Parametric study

• Non-Linear trim solver

AoA=-5°

AoA=+5°

NON-Linear
Linear

- Provides pre-stressed matrices and deformed aerodynamics for the flutter
- Still based on constrained model, working to implement free trim (mean axes)

- DLM computed on deformed geometry
- Pre-stressed stiffness matrix for the modal base computation
- Accounts for Non-linear effects, e.g. strut behavior when in compression

- Design of a WT model to investigate all these effects:
 - ✓ Froude scaling to respect the dynamic behavior
 - ✓ Incidence variation to investigate the trim effect
 - ✓ Different strut position and connection
- Polimi's WT facility:
 - ✓ Closed circuit
 - ✓ 4x4x4m test section
 - ✓ 50m/s max speed
 - ✓ turning platform on the floor
 - ✓ Model vertically mounted

WT MODEL MAIN FEATURES

Equipped with accelerometers and motion capture optical system

Adjustable connection in chordwise direction

Adjustable connection in chordwise direction

Excitation strategy under development

Glass-Fiber main spar + aluminum strut,
can be substituted by a steel cable.
Single point connection for 3D printed
aerosectors

- Test program:
 - ✓ Sweep both for AoA and V_{inf}
 - ✓ For each point flutter excitation and identification
 - ✓ Sensitivity to strut connection
 - ✓ Aluminum spar vs steel cable for strut
- Objective:
 - ✓ To map the aeroelastic behavior wrt boundary conditions and improve the knowledge about this configuration, extending the results to the full A/C

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